

РАЗДЕЛ. ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫЕ НАУКИ

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5732562>

МРНТИ 27.29.17; 27.29.25; 27.33.19

**О ЧИСЛЕННОМ РЕШЕНИИ ЗАДАЧИ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ДЛЯ
ОБЫКНОВЕННЫХ ДИФФЕРЕНЦИАЛЬНЫХ УРАВНЕНИЙ С
МНОГОТОЧЕЧНЫМ УСЛОВИЕМ**

Э.А. Бакирова,

к.ф.-м.н., проф.,

Институт математики и математического моделирования

Ж.М. Кадирбаева,

к.ф.-м.н., проф.,

МУИТ

А.Б. Касымова,

магистрант, физико-математический факультет,

КазНацЖенПУ,

г. Алматы

Аннотация: Исследуется линейная краевая задача с параметром для обыкновенных дифференциальных уравнений с многоточечным условием. Для решения рассматриваемой задачи применяется метод параметризации. На основе метода параметризации и численных методов разработан численный метод решения рассматриваемой задачи и предложены алгоритмы их реализации. Предлагается численный метод решения рассматриваемой задачи, основанный на решении построенной системы линейных алгебраических уравнений относительно параметров и метода Булирша-Штёра для решения задачи Коши на подинтервалах.

Ключевые слова: краевая задача, дифференциальное уравнение, многоточечное условие, метод параметризации

**ON A NUMERICAL SOLUTION OF THE CONTROL PROBLEM FOR
ORDINARY DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS WITH MULTIPOINT
CONDITION**

E.A. Bakirova,

Ph.D., Professor,

Institute of Mathematics and Mathematical Modeling

J.M. Kadirbaeva,

Ph.D., Professor,
Muit

A.B. Kasymova,
Master's Student, Faculty of Physics and Mathematics,
KazNacZhenPU,
Almaty city

Annotation: A linear boundary value problem with a parameter for ordinary differential equations with a multipoint condition is investigated. The parameterization method is used to solve this problem. Based on the parametrization method and numerical methods, a numerical method for solving the problem under consideration has been developed and algorithms for their implementation have been proposed. A numerical method for solving the considering problem is proposed, based on solving the constructed system of linear algebraic equations with respect to parameters and the Bulirsch-Stoer method for solving the Cauchy problem on subintervals.

Keywords: boundary value problem, differential equation, multi-point condition, parameterization method

Boundary value problems with parameters for a system of ordinary differential equations have been intensively investigated in recent years. The issues of existence, uniqueness and stability of the solution of problems with parameters are very important for the development of numerical methods for identifying the parameters of mathematical models described by ordinary differential equations with a multipoint condition. Various methods have been used [1-12] to solve these classes of control problems. Despite this, the questions of finding effective criteria for unique solvability and constructing numerical algorithms for finding optimal solutions to control problems for systems of ordinary differential equations still remain open. One of the constructive methods for investigating and solving boundary value problems with parameters for a system of ordinary differential equations is the parametrization method [13].

In this paper, we study a linear boundary value problem with a parameter for an ordinary differential equation with a multipoint condition. A numerical method for solving the problem under consideration is developed on the basis of the parameterization method and numerical methods, and algorithms for their implementation are proposed. By splitting the interval and introducing additional parameters, a linear boundary value problem with a parameter for ordinary differential equations with a multipoint condition is reduced to an equivalent boundary value problem with a parameter. An equivalent boundary value problem with parameters consists of the Cauchy problem for a system of ordinary

differential equations with parameters, a multipoint condition, and a gluing condition. The solution to the Cauchy problem for a system of ordinary differential equations with parameters is constructed using the fundamental matrix of the differential equation. Substituting the values at the corresponding points of the constructed solution into the multipoint condition and the gluing condition, a system of linear algebraic equations with respect to the parameters is compiled. A numerical method is proposed for solving the problem under consideration, based on the solution of the constructed system and the Bulirsch-Stör method for solving the Cauchy problem on subintervals.

On the interval $[0, T]$ we consider a linear boundary value problem with a parameter to a system of ordinary differential equations with multi-point condition

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = A(t)x + B(t)\mu + f(t), x \in R^n, \mu \in R^m, t \in (0, T), (1)$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^{N+1} C_i x(t_i) + D\mu = d, d \in R^{n+m}, (2)$$

where the $(n \times n)$ -matrix $A(t)$, $(n \times m)$ -matrix $B(t)$; n – vector-function $f(t)$ are continuous on $[0, T]$, the $((n + m) \times n)$ -matrices C_i , $i = \overline{0, N + 1}$, the $((n + m) \times m)$ -matrix D are constants, $0 = t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_N < t_{N+1} = T$.

The solution of the problem (1), (2) is a pair $(x^*(t), \mu^*)$, where continuous on $[0, T]$ and continuously differentiable on $(0, T)$ vector-function $x^*(t)$ satisfies the system of ordinary differential equations (1) and condition (2) for $\mu = \mu^*$.

To solve the problem with parameter (1), (2), the approach developed in [14-20] is used, based on the algorithms of the parametrization method and numerical methods for solving Cauchy problems.

Let's consider the scheme of the parametrization method. The interval $[0, T]$ is divided into N subintervals by the following points:

$$[0, T] = \bigcup_{r=\overline{1, N+1}} [t_{r-1}, t_r).$$

Let $C([0, T], R^n)$ – be the space of continuous on $[0, T]$ of functions $x: [0, T] \rightarrow R^n$ with the norm $\|x\|_1 = \max_{t \in [0, T]} \|x(t)\|$; $C([0, T], \Delta_N, R^{n(N+1)})$ – be the space of systems of functions of $x[t] = (x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_{N+1}(t))$, where $x_r: [t_{r-1}, t_r) \rightarrow R^n$ is continuous on $[t_{r-1}, t_r)$ have finite left-sided limit $\lim_{t \rightarrow t_r-0} x_r(t)$ for all $r = \overline{1, N + 1}$, with the norm $\|x[\cdot]\|_2 = \max_{r=\overline{1, N+1}} \sup_{t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r)} \|x_r(t)\|$.

The restriction of the function $x(t)$ на $[t_{r-1}, t_r)$, $r = \overline{1, N + 1}$, is denoted by $x_r(t)$, i.e. $x_r(t) = x(t)$ for all $t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r)$, $r = \overline{1, N + 1}$. Then the problem (1), (2) will go to the equivalent problem:

$$\frac{dx_r}{dt} = A(t)x_r + B(t)\mu + f(t), t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r), r = \overline{1, N+1}, (3)$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^N C_i x_{i+1}(t_i) + C_{N+1} \lim_{t \rightarrow T-0} x_{N+1}(t) + D\mu = d, (4)$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow t_s-0} x_s(t) = x_{s+1}(t_s), s = \overline{1, N}, (5)$$

where (5) are the continuity conditions on the interior points of partition $[0, T]$.

The solution of problem (3) – (5) is a pair $(x^*[t], \mu^*)$ with elements $x^*[t] = (x_1^*(t), x_2^*(t), \dots, x_{N+1}^*(t)) \in C([0, T], \Delta_N, R^{n(N+1)})$, $\mu^* \in R^m$, where the functions $x_r^*(t), r = \overline{1, N+1}$, are continuously differentiable on $[t_{r-1}, t_r)$, which satisfies system of ordinary differential equations (3) and condition (4) with $\mu = \mu^*$ and continuity conditions (5).

We introduce additional parameters $\lambda_r = x_r(t_{r-1}), r = \overline{1, N+1}$, $\lambda_{N+2} = \mu$. And on every r -th interval $[t_{r-1}, t_r), r = \overline{1, N+1}$, we replace the function $x_r(t) = u_r(t) + \lambda_r, r = \overline{1, N+1}$. Then we obtain to the equivalent boundary value problem with the parameters:

$$\frac{du_r}{dt} = A(t)[u_r + \lambda_r] + B(t)\lambda_{N+2} + f(t),$$

$$t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r), r = \overline{1, N+1}, (6)$$

$$u_r(t_{r-1}) = 0, r = \overline{1, N+1}, (7)$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^N C_i \lambda_{i+1} + C_{N+1} \lambda_{N+1} + C_{N+1} \lim_{t \rightarrow T-0} u_{N+1}(t) + D\lambda_{N+2} = d, (8)$$

$$\lambda_s + \lim_{t \rightarrow t_s-0} u_s(t) = \lambda_{s+1}, s = \overline{1, N}. (9)$$

A pair $(u^*[t], \lambda^*)$ with elements $u^*[t] = (u_1^*(t), u_2^*(t), \dots, u_{N+1}^*(t)) \in C([0, T], \Delta_N, R^{n(N+1)})$, $\lambda^* = (\lambda_1^*, \lambda_2^*, \dots, \lambda_{N+1}^*, \lambda_{N+2}^*) \in R^{n(N+1)+m}$ is called the solution of the problem (6)-(9) if the functions $u_r^*(t), r = \overline{1, N+1}$, are continuously differentiable on $[t_{r-1}, t_r)$ and for $\lambda_j = \lambda_j^*, j = \overline{1, N+2}$, satisfy the system of differential equations (6) and conditions (7)-(9).

Problems (1), (2) and (6)-(9) are equivalent. If the pair $(x^*(t), \mu^*)$ is the solution of the problem (1), (2), then the pair $(u^*[t], \lambda^*)$ with elements $u^*[t] = (u_1^*(t), u_2^*(t), \dots, u_{N+1}^*(t)) \in C([0, T], \Delta_N, R^{n(N+1)})$,

$\lambda^* = (\lambda_1^*, \lambda_2^*, \dots, \lambda_{N+1}^*, \lambda_{N+2}^*) \in R^{n(N+1)+m}$, where $\lambda_r^* = x_r^*(t_{r-1}), u_r^*(t) = x_r^*(t) + x_r^*(t_{r-1}), t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r), r = \overline{1, N+1}, \lambda_{N+2}^* = \mu^* \in R^m$, will be the solution of the problem (3)-(6). And vice versa, if the pair $(\tilde{u}[t], \tilde{\lambda})$ with elements $\tilde{u}[t] = (\tilde{u}_1(t), \tilde{u}_2(t), \dots, \tilde{u}_{N+1}(t)) \in C([0, T], \Delta_N, R^{n(N+1)})$, $\tilde{\lambda} = (\tilde{\lambda}_1, \tilde{\lambda}_2, \dots, \tilde{\lambda}_{N+2}) \in R^{n(N+1)+m}$ – is the solution of the problem (3)-(6), then the pair $(\tilde{x}(t), \tilde{\mu})$ defined by the equalities $\tilde{x}(t) = u_r(t) + \tilde{\lambda}_r, t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r), r = \overline{1, N+1}, \tilde{x}(T) =$

$\lim_{t \rightarrow T-0} \tilde{u}_N(t) + \tilde{\lambda}_N$ and $\tilde{\mu} = \tilde{\lambda}_{N+2}$, will be the solution of the original problem (1), (2).

Let $X_r(t)$ – be the fundamental matrix of the differential equation $\frac{dx}{dt} = A(t)x$ на $[t_{r-1}, t_r)$, $r = \overline{1, N+1}$. Then the solution of the Cauchy problem (6), (7) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} u_r(t) = X_r(t) & \int_{t_{r-1}}^t X_r^{-1}(\tau)A(\tau)d\tau \lambda_r \\ & + X_r(t) \int_{t_{r-1}}^t X_r^{-1}(\tau)B(\tau)d\tau \lambda_{N+2} + X_r(t) \int_{t_{r-1}}^t X_r^{-1}(\tau)f(\tau)d\tau, t \\ & \in [t_{r-1}, t_r), r = \overline{1, N+1}. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Substituting the right hand side of (10) into (8), (9) when the respective limit values, we get the following system of algebraic equations for the parameters $\lambda_r, r = \overline{1, N+2}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=0}^N C_i \lambda_{i+1} + C_{N+1} \lambda_{N+1} + D \lambda_{N+2} + C_{N+1} X_{N+1}(T) \int_{t_N}^T X_{N+1}^{-1}(\tau)A(\tau)d\tau \lambda_{N+1} \\ + C_{N+1} X_{N+1}(T) \int_{t_N}^T X_{N+1}^{-1}(\tau)B(\tau)d\tau \lambda_{N+2} \\ = d - C_{N+1} X_{N+1}(T) \int_{t_N}^T X_{N+1}^{-1}(\tau)f(\tau)d\tau, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_s + X_s(t_s) \int_{t_{s-1}}^{t_s} X_s^{-1}(\tau)A(\tau)d\tau \lambda_s + X_s(t_s) \int_{t_{s-1}}^{t_s} X_s^{-1}(\tau)B(\tau)d\tau \lambda_{N+2} \\ - \lambda_{s+1} = -X_s(t_s) \int_{t_{s-1}}^{t_s} X_s^{-1}(\tau)f(\tau)d\tau, s = \overline{1, N}. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Denoting by $Q_*(\Delta_N)$ the matrix corresponding to the left side of the system (11), (12) and composed of coefficients for the parameters $\lambda_r, r = \overline{1, N+2}$, and also entering the vector

$$\begin{aligned} F_*(\Delta_N) = \left(-d + C_{N+1} X_{N+1}(T) \int_{t_N}^T X_{N+1}^{-1}(\tau)f(\tau)d\tau, \right. \\ \left. X_1(t_1) \int_{t_0}^{t_1} X_1^{-1}(\tau)f(\tau)d\tau, \dots, X_N(t_N) \int_{t_{N-1}}^{t_N} X_N^{-1}(\tau)f(\tau)d\tau \right), \end{aligned}$$

let's write the system (11), (12) in the form

$$Q_*(\Delta_N)\lambda = -F_*(\Delta_N), \lambda \in R^{n(N+1)+m}. \quad (13)$$

It is not difficult to establish that the solvability of the boundary value problem (1), (2) is equivalent to the solvability of the system (13). The solution of system (13) is the vector $\lambda^* = (\lambda_1^*, \lambda_2^*, \dots, \lambda_{N+1}^*, \lambda_{N+2}^*) \in R^{n(N+1)+m}$ consists of the values of the solutions of the original problem (1), (2) at the initial points of the subintervals, i.e. $\lambda_r^* = x^*(t_{r-1}), r = \overline{1, N+1}, \lambda_{N+2}^* = \mu^*$.

Next, we consider Cauchy problems for ordinary differential equations on subintervals

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dz}{dt} &= A(t)z + P(t), \\ z(t_{r-1}) &= 0, t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r], r = \overline{1, N+1}, \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where $P(t) - (n \times n)$ matrix or an n vector, both continuous on $[t_{r-1}, t_r], r = \overline{1, N+1}$. Therefore, the solution of problem (14) is a square matrix or vector of dimension n . Denote by $a_r(P, t)$ the solution of the Cauchy problem (14). It is obvious that

$$a_r(P, t) = X_r(t) \int_{t_{r-1}}^t X_r^{-1}(\tau)P(\tau)d\tau, t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r],$$

where $X_r(t) -$ is the fundamental matrix of differential equation (14) on the r -th interval.

We propose the following numerical implementation of the algorithm based on the Bulirsch-Shter method.

1. Suppose we have a partition $\Delta_N: 0 = t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_N < t_{N+1} = T$. Divide each r th interval $[t_{r-1}, t_r], r = \overline{1, N+1}$, into N_r parts with $h_r = (t_r - t_{r-1})/N_r$. Suppose that at each interval $[t_{r-1}, t_r]$ the variable \hat{t} takes discrete values: $\hat{t} = t_{r-1}, \hat{t} = t_{r-1} + h_r, \dots, \hat{t} = t_{r-1} + (N_r - 1)h_r, \hat{t} = t_r$, and denote by $\{t_{r-1}, t_r\}$ the set of such points.

2. Solving the following Cauchy problems for ordinary differential equations by the Bulirsch-Stern method

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dz}{dt} &= A(t)z + A(t), z(t_{r-1}) = 0, t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r], \\ \frac{dz}{dt} &= A(t)z + B(t), z(t_{r-1}) = 0, t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r], \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{dz}{dt} = A(t)z + f(t), z(t_{r-1}) = 0, t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r], r = \overline{1, N+1},$$

we find the values of $(n \times n)$ matrices $a_r(A, \hat{t}), a_r(B, \hat{t})$ and n vector $a_r(f, \hat{t})$ on $\{t_{r-1}, t_r\}, r = \overline{1, N+1}$.

3. Construct a system of linear algebraic equations with respect to parameters

$$Q_*^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_N)\lambda = -F_*^{\tilde{h}}(\Delta_N), \lambda \in R^{n(N+1)+m}. (15)$$

Solving the system (15), we find $\lambda^{\tilde{h}}$. As noted above, the elements $\lambda^{\tilde{h}} = (\lambda_1^{\tilde{h}}, \lambda_2^{\tilde{h}}, \dots, \lambda_{N+2}^{\tilde{h}})$ are the values of the approximate solution of the problem (1), (2) at the starting points of the subintervals: $x^{\tilde{h}r}(t_{r-1}) = \lambda_r^{\tilde{h}}, r = \overline{1, N+1}, \mu^* = \lambda_{N+2}^*$.

4. To determine the values of the approximate solution at the remaining points of the set $\{t_{r-1}, t_r\}$, it is necessary to solve the Cauchy problems

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = A(t)x + B(t)\lambda_{N+2}^{\tilde{h}} + f(t),$$

$$x(t_{r-1}) = \lambda_r^{\tilde{h}}, t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r], r = \overline{1, N+1}.$$

And solutions to the Cauchy problem can be found by the Bulirsch-Shter method. Thus, the algorithm allows us to find a numerical solution to the problem (1), (2).

To illustrate the proposed approach for the numerical solving of a linear boundary value problem with a parameter for an ordinary differential equation with a multipoint condition (1), (2) based on the parametrization method, let us consider the following example.

Example. We consider on the interval $[0,1]$ a linear boundary value problem with a parameter for a system of ordinary differential equations with a multipoint condition

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = A(t)x + B(t)\mu + f(t), x \in R^2, \mu \in R^3, t \in (0,1), (16)$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^4 C_i x(t_i) + D\mu = d, d \in R^5. (17)$$

where $t_0 = 0, t_1 = \frac{1}{4}, t_2 = \frac{1}{2}, t_3 = \frac{3}{4}, t_4 = 1,$

$$A(t) = \begin{pmatrix} t-2 & e^{2t} \\ 1 & t \end{pmatrix}, B(t) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(t) & 6t & t^2 \\ 0 & 2 & 3t \end{pmatrix},$$

$$C_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 0 \\ -4 & 3 \\ 1 & 6 \\ 3 & 7 \end{pmatrix}, C_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 1 \\ 5 & 2 \\ 3 & 0 \\ 8 & -6 \\ 1 & 9 \end{pmatrix}, C_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 5 & 3 \\ 1 & 7 \\ 11 & 0 \\ 4 & 6 \\ -4 & 2 \end{pmatrix}, C_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 11 & 0 \\ 6 & 13 \\ 4 & 7 \\ -5 & 2 \\ 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix}, C_4 =$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} -6 & 1 \\ 5 & 3 \\ 8 & 1 \\ 2 & 6 \\ 0 & 9 \end{pmatrix}, D = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 3 & 0 \\ 3 & 1 & -4 \\ 0 & 7 & -6 \\ -2 & 1 & 8 \\ 6 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, d = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1155}{16} \\ \frac{7511}{16} \\ \frac{64}{6479} \\ \frac{64}{16545} \\ \frac{64}{1633} \\ \frac{16}{16} \end{pmatrix},$$

$$f(t) = \left(4 \cos(t) - 2e^{2t} - 30t - 22t^2 + 2t^3 - t^4 - 6t^2 e^{2t} + 6 \right) \cdot \frac{-7t^3 - 53t - 14}{-7t^3 - 53t - 14}$$

We use a numerical implementation of the proposed algorithm. We provide the results of the numerical implementation of the algorithm by partitioning the subintervals [0, 0,25], [0,25, 0,5], [0,5, 0,75], [0,75, 1] in increments of h = 0.025.

Solving the system of equations (15), we obtain the numerical values of the parameters

$$\lambda_1^{\tilde{h}} = \begin{pmatrix} -0.0000000074 \\ 1.99999999221 \end{pmatrix}, \lambda_2^{\tilde{h}} = \begin{pmatrix} 1.5156250169 \\ 2.3749999268 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\lambda_3^{\tilde{h}} = \begin{pmatrix} 3.1250000222 \\ 3.4999999439 \end{pmatrix}, \lambda_4^{\tilde{h}} = \begin{pmatrix} 4.9218750227 \\ 5.3749999728 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\lambda_5^{\tilde{h}} = \tilde{\mu} = \begin{pmatrix} -3.9999997908 \\ 6.999999984 \\ 19.0000000642 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Numerical solutions at other points of the subintervals are found by the Runge-Kutta method of the 4th order solving the following Cauchy problems

$$\frac{d\tilde{x}_r}{dt} = A(t)\tilde{x}_r + B(t)\lambda_5^{\tilde{h}} + f(t),$$

$$x(t_{r-1}) = \lambda_r^{\tilde{h}}, t \in [t_{r-1}, t_r], r = 1: 4.$$

The exact solution of the problem (16), (17) is the pair $(x^*(t), \mu^*)$, where

$$x^*(t) = \begin{pmatrix} t^3 + 6t \\ 6t^2 + 2 \end{pmatrix}, \mu^* = \begin{pmatrix} -4 \\ 7 \\ 19 \end{pmatrix}.$$

For the difference between the corresponding values of the exact and constructed solutions of the problem, the following estimate is valid:

$$\max_{j=\overline{0,40}} \|x^*(t_j) - \tilde{x}(t_j)\| < 7 \cdot 10^{-8}, \text{ and } \|\mu^* - \tilde{\mu}\| < 2 \cdot 10^{-8}.$$

The paper proposes a parametrization method for solving a linear boundary value problem with a parameter for ordinary differential equations with a

multipoint condition. A numerical method for solving the problem under consideration is proposed, based on solving the constructed system of linear algebraic equations with respect to parameters and the Bulirsch-Shter method for solving the Cauchy problem on subintervals.

Bibliography

- [1] Kiguradze I.T. Kraevye zadachi dlya system obiknovennykh differential'nykh uravneniy. / I.T. Kiguradze. // Itogi nauki i tekhn. Ser. Sovrem. probl. mat. Nov. dostizh. – 1987. T. 30. 3-103 p.
- [2] Ronto M. Numerical analytic methods in the theory of boundary-value problems. / M. Ronto, A.M. Samoilenko. // World Scientific, River Edge. – 2000.
- [3] Boichuk A.A. Generalized inverse operators and Fredholm boundary-value problems. / A.A. Boichuk, A.M. Samoilenko. // VSP. – 2004.
- [4] Brunner H. Collocation methods for Volterra integral and related functional equations. / H. Brunner. // Cambridge University Press. – 2004.
- [5] Wazwaz A.M. Linear and Nonlinear Integral Equations: Methods and Applications. / A.M. Wazwaz. // Higher Equation Press. – 2011.
- [6] Loreti P. Control problems for weakly coupled systems with memory. / P. Loreti, D. Sforza. // J. of Diff. Equat. – 2014. Vol. 257. 1879-1938 p.
- [7] Dzhumabaev D.S. An algorithm for solving a control problem for a differential equation with a parameter. / D.S. Dzhumabaev, E.A. Bakirova, Zh.M. Kadirbayeva. // News of the NAS RK. Phys.-Math. Series. – 2018. Vol. 5. № 321. 25-32 p.
- [8] Assanova A.T. Numerical implementation of solving a boundary value problem for a system of loaded differential equations with parameter. / A.T. Assanova, E.A. Bakirova, Zh.M. Kadirbayeva. // News of the NAS RK. Phys.-Math. Series. – 2019. Vol. 3. № 325. 77-84 p.
- [9] Assanova A.T. Numerically approximate method for solving of a control problem for integro-differential equations of parabolic type. / A.T. Assanova, E.A. Bakirova, Zh.M. Kadirbayeva. // News of the NAS RK. Phys.-Math. Series. – 2019. Vol. 6. № 328. 14-24 p.
- [10] Assanova A.T. Numerical solution of a control problem for ordinary differential equations with multipoint integral condition. / A.T. Assanova, E.A. Bakirova, Zh.M. Kadirbayeva. // International Journal of Mathematics and Physics. – 2019. Vol. 10, № 2. 4-10 p.
- [11] Assanova A.T. Numerical solution to a control problem for integro-differential equations. / A.T. Assanova, E.A. Bakirova, Zh.M. Kadirbayeva. // Computational mathematics and mathematical physics. – 2020. Vol. 60. №2. 203-221 p.

[12] Assanova A.T. computational method for solving a problem with parameter for linear systems of integro-differential equations. / A.T. Assanova, E.A. Bakirova, Zh.M. Kadirbayeva, R.E. Uteshova. // Computational and Applied Mathematics. – 2020. Vol. 39. № 3.

[13] Dzhumabaev D.S. Criteria for the unique solvability of a linear boundary-value problem for an ordinary differential equation. / D.S. Dzhumabaev. // USSR Comput. Math. Math. Phys. – 1989. Vol. 29. № 1. 34-46 p.

[14] Dzhumabaev D.S. On one approach to solve the linear boundary value problems for Fredholm integro-differential equations. / D.S. Dzhumabaev. // Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics. – 2016. Vol. 294. 342-357 p.

[15] Dzhumabaev D.S. Computational methods of solving the boundary value problems for the loaded differential and Fredholm integro-differential equations. / D.S. Dzhumabaev. // Mathematical Methods in the Applied Sciences. – 2018. Vol. 41. № 4. 1439-1462 p.

[16] Dzhumabaev D.S. Well-posedness of nonlocal boundary value problem for a system of loaded hyperbolic equations and an algorithm for finding its solution. / D.S. Dzhumabaev. // Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications. – 2018. Vol. 461. № 1. 817-836 p.

[17] Dzhumabaev D.S. New general solutions to linear Fredholm integro-differential equations and their applications on solving the boundary value problems. / D.S. Dzhumabaev. // Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics. – 2018. Vol. 327. № 1. 79-108 p.

[18] Kadirbayeva Zh.M. Zhai differentsialdik tendeler zhuiesi ushin kopnukteli shettik esepi sheshudin sandyk zhuzege asyrylyu. / Zh.M. Kadirbayeva, D.K. Mirzakhmet. // Vestnik KazNITU, Fiziko-matematicheskie nauki. – 2018. №2 (126). 495-502 p.

[19] Bakirova E.A. Zhai differentsialdik tendeler zhuiesi ushin sizikti kopnukteli shettik esepin birmandi sheshilimdiligi. / E.A. Bakirova, Zh.M. Kadirbayeva, K.P. Kenzhebaeva. // Vestnik KazNITU, Fiziko-matematicheskie nauki. – 2016. № 6(118). 332-338 p.

[20] Kadirbayeva Zh.M. On the method for solving linear boundary-value problem for the system of loaded differential equations with multipoint integral condition. / Zh.M. Kadirbayeva. // Mathematical Journal. – 2017. Vol. 17. № 4. 50-61 p.

© E.A. Bakirova, J.M. Kadirbaeva, A.B. Kasymova, 2021

Поступила в редакцию 04.10.2021
Принята к публикации 15.10.2021

Для цитирования:

Бакирова Э.А., Кадирбаева Ж.М., Касымова А.Б. О численном решении задачи управления для обыкновенных дифференциальных уравнений с многоточечным условием // Инновационные научные исследования. 2021. № 10-2(12). С. 5-15. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>